

THE ROLE AND HISTORY OF THE UTILITY SECTOR IN SOCIETY**Allambergenov Azamat Tilewbergenovich****Turgaev Jambil**

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Abstract. This article describes the role and history of the utility sector in society, construction of facilities.

Keywords: communal economy, building construction, housing, infrastructure.

РОЛЬ И ИСТОРИЯ КОММУНАЛЬНОГО ХОЗЯЙСТВА В ОБЩЕСТВЕ

Аннотация. В данной статье описывается роль и история коммунального хозяйства в обществе, строительстве объектов.

Ключевые слова: коммунальное хозяйство, жилищное строительство, жилье, инфраструктура.

From the first days of the independence of our republic until now, the introduction of free market relations in all areas of the economy and the development of contractual relations based on an environment of free competition are being carried out intensively. During the short period of time, an economic mechanism was formed in our republic, which incorporated local characteristics and was aimed at raising the standard of living of the population and ensuring the well-being of the people as a result. Under the leadership of the President, I.A.

In this work, as well as in many works of our President, the ideas aimed at reforming our national economy and its various sectors, directions and components are interpreted, and in essence, the expected result of the reforms implemented in our country is production in an environment of free market relations and pure competition. As President I.A. Karimov said, the best result of this is the development of the service sector, "the rise of the economic potential of our Republic, the comfortable living of our people, and the creation of suitable conditions for our youth to grow into mature and well-rounded people"¹. Since the essence of the economic reforms being carried out in our country is to ensure the well-being of the people, first of all, ensuring the development of the social sphere, the development of housing and communal economy, which is an important part of it, remains one of the main tasks.

During the historical development of mankind, one of the main and important tasks has been the issue of improving the standard of living of the population. The standard of living of the

population depends on the availability of material goods related to living and the level of organization of services provided in the social sphere. In turn, spiritual and material blessings are the product of human thinking, the result of effective work. Currently, according to the method adopted by the United Nations, the rating of the level of development of the countries of the world is determined not according to their economic potential or military power, but according to the level of development of the population's living culture and human resources. The standard of living of the population depends on the social policy and the development of the social sector in the country. In turn, the social sphere consists of infrastructures that provide material and spiritual benefits to the population. If areas such as education, culture, art, sports and health care serve to educate the population as a perfect person, the development of the housing and communal services system creates conditions for the population to live a comfortable life and form a decent lifestyle.

When studying the world population statistics, a century ago, in 1900, it was recorded that 1,608 million people lived on earth, and a century later, in 2000, it can be seen that the population reached 5,300 million people. Of course, the growth of the population was due to the development of science and technology, the development of the medical field, and the fact that it was possible to treat the epidemics that destroyed the population. The field of housing and communal services plays an important role in creating a favorable opportunity for the education of disabled children.

When we look at the history of housing construction and communal economy, we witness the existence of a school with a long history and unlimited resources in this field in our country. Even if we look at the "Mausoleum of the Samonites" in the historical monument built by our ancestors, which is considered the oldest in Central Asia (10th century, in 980s), it is an architectural monument created at the level of a unique work of art. We will see the presence of a road that protects against damage, a drainage system, and communications that provide air circulation. We can see that there was a certain experience in the construction of engineering networks in Central Asia at that time. According to the results of archaeological excavations conducted by Uzbek-Japanese scientists in the area of the city of Dalvarzintepa in Surkhandarya region, which is considered the oldest in Central Asia, it became known that water supply to this city was carried out through special clay pipes. In Shahrisabz, a beautiful garden was built on the roof of the Oksaroy ensemble, built by our great grandfather Amir Temir, and clear water flowed from the favora (fountain) in the middle of the garden. The water pipe to this favora was brought from a spring coming out of the mountain rock through ceramic pipes, and the pipes were welded to each other by melting lead. Also, water supply and sewage pipeline networks can be found in every historical monument preserved in our ancient cities such as Bukhara, Samarkand, Khiva.

However, the scientific aspects of the engineering communication systems preserved in the

historical monuments inherited from our ancestors in our country have not been fully studied until now. The water supply facility, built in the XV-XVI centuries in the Nurota district of Samarkand region, has a total length of more than 10 km and is located at a depth of 10-35 meters from the surface of the earth. Since ancient times (XI-XVII centuries) in the territory of Central Asia, the scarcity of water sources and the dry and hot natural climatic conditions, the rational use of water resources, the engineering designed to accumulate large amounts of water reserves during periods of natural precipitation and maintain them for a long time led to the creation of structures.

In the scientific research conducted along the map of the ancient Great Silk Road, it was found that in the part of this historical road that passed through the deserts of Central Asia, the constructions called Cisterns, which served to provide drinking water to trade caravans, were built. determined. The results of the scientific research of the cisterns that have survived to this day show that they have the ability to collect enough water until the end of the spring rainy season, until the next autumn rainy season, protect them from sunlight and pollution, and prevent the spread of infectious diseases and harmful bacteria. it shows that the construction of facilities is very perfect and scientifically based. In the territory of Central Asia, there are dozens of engineering structures whose dates of construction and commissioning date back to the previous millennium, all of them in the distant past of ancient cities and permanent (middle) in the territory of Central Asia. troq) indicates that housing and agricultural water supply facilities were built in residential areas, and that the foundation of the housing and communal services sector was established in Central Asia.

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